

Nuclear data uncertainty propagation on the beta effective. Impact of the precursor abundances and new covariance matrices from the ALDEN experiment

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ABSTRACT

Accurate estimation of the effective delayed neutron fraction is essential in reactor-physics analyses. While previous studies have quantified the contribution of major nuclear data uncertainties to effective delayed neutron fraction, the impact of delayed precursor abundances has remained insufficiently characterized due to the historical lack of covariance data. This work makes use of the new precursor-abundance covariance matrices recently evaluated in the ALDEN experimental program, enabling, for the first time, the propagation of uncertainties associated with precursor abundances of Uranium 235 and Plutonium 239 in a complex PWR mixed-core configuration (EPICURE UM17×17). Sensitivity analyses and uncertainty quantification show that, although the sensitivities of effective delayed fraction to precursor abundances are comparable in magnitude to those of fission and delayed multiplicity data, strong anti-correlations between precursor families suppress their total propagated effect by nearly an order of magnitude. As a result, precursor-abundance uncertainties contribute only around 0.5% to the overall uncertainty, confirming delayed neutron multiplicity as the dominant source.

Keywords: beta effective, covariance, abundance, uncertainty

1. INTRODUCTION

Beta effective is a key parameter for reactor safety. It represents the fraction of neutrons, among those emitted by fissions, that are emitted on a longer time scale. Those neutrons, which are emitted on a time scale that ranges from a few tenths of a second to a minute, are called delayed neutrons, in contrast to those emitted almost instantaneously, which are called prompt neutrons.

In a typical water reactor, delayed neutrons account for less than 1% of the overall neutron population, but, as long as the reactor does not become prompt-critical, they keep the doubling time of the reactor in the range of seconds, playing a key role in its controllability.

The complete description of how to compute the beta effective is beyond the scope of this paper, but can be found in the following references [1, 2]. Here, we will limit ourselves to recalling its formulation, which is the following:

$$\beta_{eff} = \sum_k \frac{\sum_i \int_0^\infty \phi^+(E) \chi_{d,k}(E) dE \int_0^\infty a_{k,i}(E) \overline{v_{d,i}}(E) \Sigma_{f,i}(E) \phi(E) dE}{\sum_i \int_0^\infty \phi^+(E) \chi_{t,i}(E) dE \int_0^\infty \overline{v_{t,i}}(E) \Sigma_{f,i}(E) \phi(E) dE} \quad (1)$$

where ϕ is the neutron flux, ϕ^+ the adjoint flux, $v_{t,i}$ and $v_{d,i}$ are respectively the total and delayed neutron multiplicity for isotope i , $\chi_{t,i}$ the total fission spectra of isotope i , $\chi_{d,k}$ the delayed fission spectra of precursor family k , $a_{k,i}$ is the abundance of family k for isotope i and $\Sigma_{f,i}$ is the macroscopic fission cross section of isotope i .

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As can be seen in equation 1, to compute the beta effective, in addition to the forward and adjoint fluxes and the nuclear data needed for the calculation of these two fluxes, we also need delayed nuclear data, which are nuclear data relative to the neutrons that are emitted on a delayed time scale.

The specificity of delayed nuclear data is that, since those data are not relevant in steady-state situations, they can be overlooked in situations or experiments that are at equilibrium.

This work aims to provide further insight into the uncertainty of delayed nuclear data and their propagation on the beta effective, with a focus on the propagation of the uncertainties of the abundances obtained thanks to the new evaluations of the ALDEN (Average Lifetime of DELayed Neutrons) experiment [3].

2. EPICURE

The EPICURE program (1989-1994) was jointly agreed upon 1988 by the CEA and its industrial partners. The program consisted in 5 configurations (UH1.2, UH1.4, UH1.4-abs, MH1.2, UM-17 × 17, UM-Zone). The UMZONE core is representative of real conditions in a PWR mixed core containing a central MOX assembly surrounded by UO₂ assemblies [4].

The 17 × 17 MOX assembly is zoned and comprises 25 guide tubes and 264 fuel pins: 100 MOX pins with an 8.7% Pu content in the center, 100 pins with a 7% Pu content in intermediate locations, and 64 pins with a 4.3% Pu content in an outer ring in contact with the surrounding UO₂ pins.

Since Uranium and Plutonium have very different delayed neutron fractions, this configuration is particularly challenging for what concerns beta effective calculations. Indeed, the effective delayed fraction depends not only on the neutron flux spectrum but also on its spatial distribution.

A model aimed at simulating this configuration is shown in Figure 1.

This model has already been used in previous works [1, 5, 6], and it has been shown to be able to provide robust results, both in terms of beta effective calculation and sensitivities.

The value of the beta effective computed for this configuration is 647 pcm, of which 458 pcm are due to fission of Uranium 235, 113 pcm are due to Uranium 238, 53 pcm to Plutonium 239, 23 pcm to Plutonium 241, and the remaining contributions add up to less than 1 pcm.

3. PREVIOUS WORK

To propagate the uncertainties due to nuclear data on the beta effective, one needs to compute its sensitivity. To do that, one can rely on the general perturbation theory (GPT) [7, 8, 9]. Some previous work [5, 6] already computed the sensitivity of the beta effective for this configuration, and the results obtained thanks to the APOLLO3 code are shown in table I.

These sensitivities are obtained thanks to the code APOLLO3 [10], and they have been obtained using the nuclear library JEFF 3.1.1 [11].

Thanks to the covariance matrices from the COMAC covariance library [12] it has also been possible to propagate the uncertainty on the beta effective and those results are shown in table II.

These results, while including many of the major contributions, such as those from the fission cross sections and delayed and total multiplicities, do not take into consideration the contribution of delayed spectra and abundances due to the lack of relative uncertainties and covariance matrices at the time the study was performed.

Table I. Sensitivities (in %/%) of beta effective for the Epicure UM17x17 experiment.

Isotope	Capture	Elastic	Inelastic	NXN	Fission	ν_{tot}	ν_{D}
¹ H	-1.46 e-2	-8.51 e-2	-	-	-	-	-
¹⁶ O	2.30 e-3	-2.40 e-2	-3.38 e-4	-2.35 e-6	-	-	-
⁹⁰ Zr	1.25 e-4	-2.62 e-3	-3.13 e-3	-3.93 e-6	-	-	-
⁹¹ Zr	-2.07 e-4	-5.23 e-4	-9.65 e-4	-1.80 e-5	-	-	-
⁹² Zr	6.04 e-6	-7.20 e-4	-1.69 e-3	-2.03 e-5	-	-	-
⁹⁴ Zr	4.72 e-5	-7.16 e-4	-1.76 e-3	-3.36 e-5	-	-	-
²³⁵ U	-3.31 e-2	-1.41 e-4	-5.56 e-4	-3.07 e-5	1.07 e-1	-4.39 e-1	7.06 e-1
²³⁸ U	-2.94 e-3	-5.78 e-3	-3.29 e-2	-1.73 e-3	6.47 e-2	-1.30 e-1	1.74 e-1
²³⁹ Pu	6.46 e-2	-4.76 e-5	-2.21 e-4	-1.09 e-5	-1.51 e-1	-3.58 e-1	8.24 e-2
²⁴⁰ Pu	4.48 e-2	-1.91 e-5	-1.16 e-4	-3.20 e-6	-3.25 e-3	-5.25 e-3	1.02 e-3
²⁴¹ Pu	6.94 e-3	-5.95 e-6	-3.17 e-5	-6.48 e-6	-8.40 e-3	-6.33 e-2	3.48 e-2
²⁴² Pu	5.08 e-3	-8.94 e-6	-3.16 e-5	-1.53 e-6	-4.18 e-4	-9.49 e-4	3.61 e-4
²⁴¹ Am	1.09 e-2	-2.18 e-6	-1.72 e-5	-1.75 e-7	-6.81 e-4	-9.60 e-4	8.93 e-5

Table II. Uncertainty propagation (in %) of beta effective for the Epicure UM17x17 experiment. Negative values stand for imaginary values, negative contribution to the overall variance.

Isotope	Capture	Elastic	Inelastic	NXN	Fission	ν_{tot}	ν_{D}	χ	TOTAL
¹ H	0.04	0.14	0.00	0.00	-	-	-	-	0.15
¹⁶ O	0.05	0.08	0.00	0.00	-	-	-	-	0.10
⁹⁰ Zr	0.00	0.01	0.02	0.00	-	-	-	-	0.02
⁹¹ Zr	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.00	-	-	-	-	0.01
⁹² Zr	0.00	0.01	0.01	0.00	-	-	-	-	0.01
⁹⁴ Zr	0.00	0.01	0.01	0.00	-	-	-	-	0.01
²³⁵ U	0.04	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.04	-0.07	2.23	0.11	2.23
²³⁸ U	0.01	0.00	0.15	0.04	0.02	0.04	0.57	0.04	0.60
²³⁹ Pu	0.10	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.13	-0.04	0.50	0.16	0.55
²⁴⁰ Pu	0.07	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.02	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.08
²⁴¹ Pu	0.02	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.01	0.03	0.17	0.10	0.20
²⁴² Pu	0.06	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.06
²⁴¹ Am	0.03	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.00	0.03
TOTAL	0.16	0.16	0.16	0.04	0.14	-0.06	2.36	0.22	2.39

Figure 1. EPICURE UM 17x17 quarter geometry.

4. NEW COVARIANCE DATA

The ALDEN (Average Lifetime of DELayed Neutrons) experiment, built in a collaboration between CEA and CNRS, aimed at re-measuring the DN data associated with several fissioning systems (average delayed-neutron yield and kinetic parameters).

This experiment, among the new measurements and evaluation of several delayed nuclear data, also provided new uncertainties and covariance matrices related to the delayed abundances that were lacking before.

The two main matrices relevant for this work are the one in table III that is relative to the Uranium 235 [3],

and the one in table IV relative to the Plutonium 239 [13].

From both tables, we can see that, while each abundance value has a variance that ranges from a few percent to up to 30 percent, the entire correlation matrix is fully populated and shows a regular anti-correlation between close precursor families.

5. NEW RESULTS

Thanks to the implementation in APOLLO3 [5], it has been possible to compute the sensitivities of the beta effective to the delayed precursors' abundances. The results relative to the Uranium 235 and Plutonium 239, for the system mentioned before, are shown in table V.

Table III. Fitted parameters and correlation matrix for ^{235}U (Expérience ALDEN).

Parameter	Fitted value \pm unc.	a_1	a_2	a_3	a_4	a_5	a_6	a_7	a_8
a_1	0.0301 ± 0.0048	1.000	-0.970	0.916	-0.815	0.744	-0.678	0.665	-0.656
a_2	0.1558 ± 0.0153	-0.970	1.000	-0.984	0.892	-0.784	0.700	-0.665	0.634
a_3	0.0892 ± 0.0143	0.916	-0.984	1.000	-0.929	0.808	-0.718	0.668	-0.629
a_4	0.1933 ± 0.0097	-0.815	0.892	-0.929	1.000	-0.946	0.847	-0.735	0.644
a_5	0.3232 ± 0.0137	0.744	-0.784	0.808	-0.946	1.000	-0.948	0.828	-0.733
a_6	0.1008 ± 0.0159	-0.678	0.700	-0.718	0.847	-0.948	1.000	-0.947	0.857
a_7	0.0821 ± 0.0165	0.665	-0.665	0.668	-0.735	0.828	-0.947	1.000	-0.965
a_8	0.0254 ± 0.0086	-0.656	0.634	-0.629	0.644	-0.733	0.857	-0.965	1.000

 Table IV. Fitted parameters and correlation matrix for ^{239}Pu (Expérience ALDEN).

Parameter	Fitted value \pm unc.	a_1	a_2	a_3	a_4	a_5	a_6	a_7	a_8
a_1	0.0263 ± 0.0018	1.000	-0.942	0.883	-0.486	0.239	-0.103	0.050	-0.057
a_2	0.2381 ± 0.0063	-0.942	1.000	-0.953	0.638	-0.325	0.157	-0.025	-0.043
a_3	0.0814 ± 0.0064	0.883	-0.953	1.000	-0.770	0.510	-0.322	0.194	-0.146
a_4	0.1825 ± 0.0058	-0.486	0.638	-0.770	1.000	-0.870	0.681	-0.422	0.237
a_5	0.2847 ± 0.0101	0.239	-0.325	0.510	-0.870	1.000	-0.926	0.731	-0.558
a_6	0.1006 ± 0.0123	-0.103	0.157	-0.322	0.681	-0.926	1.000	-0.885	0.683
a_7	0.0464 ± 0.0146	0.050	-0.025	0.194	-0.422	0.731	-0.885	1.000	-0.922
a_8	0.0399 ± 0.0106	-0.057	-0.043	-0.146	0.237	-0.558	0.683	-0.922	1.000

Table V. Sensitivities (in %/%) of beta effective for the Epicure UM17x17 experiment due to abundances.

Isotope	a_1	a_2	a_3	a_4	a_5	a_6	a_7	a_8
^{235}U	2.40 e-02	1.07 e-01	6.67 e-02	1.40 e-01	2.31 e-01	6.43 e-02	5.80 e-02	1.62 e-02
^{239}Pu	2.60 e-03	1.92 e-02	7.10 e-03	1.44 e-02	2.53 e-02	5.90 e-03	6.42 e-03	1.49 e-03

Thanks to these sensitivities, it has been possible to propagate the uncertainties shown in table III and IV. The results are summarized in table VI, which shows the total uncertainty computed using the CO-MAC covariance library [12], the individual contribution due to the propagation of the uncertainties on the abundances of Uranium 235 [3] and Plutonium 239 [13], and the overall new value of the uncertainty.

Table VI. Uncertainty propagation (in %) of beta effective for the Epicure UM17x17 experiment relative to the abundances covariances of ^{235}U and ^{239}Pu .

	Total without a	^{235}U a	^{239}Pu a	Total
Unc	2.39	0.53	0.07	2.45

Overall, the results show that the abundances have very little impact on the overall total uncertainty. They also show that correlations are fundamental to reduce their impact; indeed, while the sensitivities to the abundances are in the same order of magnitude as those relative to fission and delayed multiplicity, the correlation between the uncertainties of the abundances contributes to decreasing the total contribution by almost an order of magnitude.

6. CONCLUSIONS

Overall, these results contribute to deepening the understanding of the impact of nuclear data uncertainties on reactor physics, in particular regarding the effective delayed neutron fraction. The results show that, while the overall uncertainty is largely dominated by the one coming from delayed multiplicity, these contributions, which are usually neglected, are the second major contributors in terms of magnitude.

These results, while allowing us to compute these terms, also allow us to provide some insight into what is still missing in this propagation. First of all, the propagation of the uncertainties on the abundances of Uranium 238 and Plutonium 241 is still missing due to the lack of their evaluation within the ALDEN project. This propagation can still be done using the covariances recommended by the IAEA [14], but it seems reasonable to expect their overall contribution to be in the same order as Plutonium 239, which exhibits a similar sensitivity.

For delayed spectra, their uncertainties and covariances are still missing. It is, however, possible to compute their sensitivities, which, while differing in energy dependence, have the same overall one-group values of the sensitivities to the abundances. Therefore, it seems reasonable to expect their final contribution to be of the same order of magnitude.

Finally, while all these contributions happen to be of second order compared to those due to the delayed neutron multiplicity of the main fissile isotopes, a new evaluation of delayed multiplicity can lead to a situation where they become comparable in terms of magnitude, and their inclusion in the overall uncertainty becomes important.

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